

THE ESSENTIAL FEATURES OF TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH THE MODERN APPROACHES AND METHODS BY USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

*N. Karimova*¹

Abstract:

The considered features of the use of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages in the materials of educational websites help to better understand the needs of students and allow teachers to build a training course in accordance with the tasks. This article reflects recent developments in the content and ways of using digital technologies in foreign language teaching, as well as young scholars who are just starting their dissertation research.

Key words: foreign languages, educational websites, training, digital technologies.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/cawazp41>

Introduction

In recent years, teaching foreign languages cannot be imagined without the use of digital technologies, and the pedagogical community must follow new trends in their development. Today, many educational sites and CD ROMs are offered to help teachers develop receptive (reading, listening) and productive (writing, speaking) competencies. Using them is an undoubted advantage in learning a foreign language. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the literature on the indicated topic and identify the latest trends in the use of digital technologies in foreign language teaching with the help of educational websites. This article reflects recent changes in the content and methods of using digital technologies in foreign language teaching, and will also be useful for young scholars who are just starting their dissertation research. Literature Review Undoubtedly, the impact of digital transformation on all areas of human life is felt very strongly. Digital transformations provide innovative tools not only for the dissemination of knowledge but also for mastering the strategies of teaching subjects in general and teaching foreign languages in particular: access to information, exchange of messages, access to documentary resources, communication in real-time interactive and multimedia sharing. The idea that digital transformations can help develop some cognitive approaches is not new. Authors including D. X. Jonassen, R. B. Kozma, R.D. Pea, G. Salomon have contributed greatly to the promotion of digital learning in education, especially in order to show how students can manage concepts using the above technologies and models.

Main body

A study by Besta (British Agency for Information and Communication Technology in Education) in the UK highlights the role of teachers in the use of digital warming in education and their impact on student achievement. M. Gus, D. Johnson and R. Johnson in their work focused on the effectiveness of working

¹ *Karimova Nigina Sunnatillo qizi, Samarqand davlat chet tillari instituti*

in small groups in conducting lessons using digital transformation. M. Connell examined the effectiveness of training by comparing traditional-style lessons with CT lessons. According to the results of the study, which lasted for several months, teaching using digital technologies showed significantly greater success. This prompted the author to think about the true cognitive potential of CT. R. Gregoire, R. Bracewell, and T. Laferrière believed that digital transformation allows the diversification of goals, methods, and learning outcomes. Approaches to teaching a foreign language using digital transformation are as rich as many authentic audio and video materials on the World Wide Web. On the other hand, Internet resources are effective because they can be updated, which provides access to truly up-to-date information, unlike paper curricula that quickly become outdated. Digital transformations in communication accelerate the development of social competencies in the target language. E-mail, WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, etc. offer a platform for real communication between students and teachers for administrative and pedagogical purposes. Although emails remain a private communication, discussion chats allow everyone to participate in the discussion and respond within a defined topic. According to the scientific views of researchers such as K. Depauer, T. Karsenti, and V. Komis, digital transformations provide an opportunity to revise and transfer the exchange between teachers and students to space and time, thereby creating new opportunities for study and/or professional training. It is also a significant potential for innovation in education and an almost limitless supply of new methods for teachers and the entire education system. Some studies show that students are more motivated to engage in learning activities using digital transformation than traditional classroom approaches, and this interest is due to the fact that these technologies allow diversification of goals, methods, materials, projects, and learning outcomes. Digital transformations allow students and teachers not only to present and receive informational knowledge using various media formats but also to learn, produce, communicate, analyze and transform them. However, many teachers today use DT mainly or even exclusively as an informational tool, which limits the pedagogical changes that the use of DT can contribute to. In the local pedagogical and psychological literature, many scientists have dealt with the use of digital transformation in education. I. G. Zakharova developed a gradation of special education programs from the point of view of didactics. The author analyzed the possibilities of integrating digital transformation into the educational process.

The possibilities for using digital technologies are enormous. The global network creates conditions for finding any necessary information: materials about the culture of the country of the studied language, news, publications, and literature of an artistic and scientific nature. Students can participate in online tests, quizzes, contests, and Olympiads. However, the introduction of the aforementioned digital transformations into the educational process does not exclude traditional ways and methods of teaching. They should be combined with the use of digital transformation at all stages of the educational process, which can greatly increase the effectiveness of learning, encourage students to improve themselves, and help them learn to move freely in the information space. In teaching a foreign language at the university, the possibilities of using digital transformation, which allows increasing the motivation of students to study, develop the skills of independent learning of a foreign language, and

reduce the level of anxiety, were considered in their scientific works of N.L. Shamne and A.N. Sovgenin. In particular, the authors analyzed the problems and prospects of using educational technologies based on digital and mobile applications. Through the use of modern digital technologies, students are increasingly provided with opportunities to develop reflective thinking related to FL learning and use (email or forum posting). As a result of this activity, students expand and improve their cognitive skills, as well as more fully apply learning strategies.

Conclusion

Undoubtedly, digital transformations play an important role in people's lives today, especially in the field of education. Indeed, the superiority of digital transformation is felt in all disciplines, be it social, religious, medical, or other fields. Foreign languages are not alone in this matter. Today, it is impossible to talk about teaching a foreign language without the use of digital technologies, which gives an advantage to the teacher and the teacher. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize the need for the teacher to use this interesting and effective tool effectively in order to motivate the students by making the lessons livelier and more colorful. This is related to a request for training and education of foreign language teachers in the field of digital technology. However, due to insufficient preparation, many teachers do not dare to fully integrate digital communication technologies into their teaching practice. Integrating digital technologies into foreign language teaching is a complex pedagogical innovation. This requires changing several aspects: teachers' habits (increasing the efficiency of computer use), revision of traditional pedagogical methods (student-oriented pedagogy; redefining the role of the teacher) and teaching tools. In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of digital transformation in foreign language teaching is considered in the materials of educational websites. characteristics help to better understand the needs of students and allow teachers to competently build the curriculum. assigned tasks.

References:

- [1]. Jonassen DH *Computers in the Classroom: Mind tools for Critical Thinking*. – Englewood Cliffs, NJ, Prentice-Hall, 1996. – 291 p.
- [2]. Kozma RB *Will media influence learning? Reframing the debate // Educational Technology Research and Development*. - 1994. - 42(2). – P. 7–19.
- [3]. Pea RD *Beyond amplification: Using the computer to reorganize mental functioning // Educational Psychologist*. - 1985. - 20(4). – P. 67–182.
- [4]. Salomon G. *New information technologies in education // Encyclopedia of Educational Research (Sixth Edition) / Ed. MC Alkin*. - New York: Macmillan, 1992. - P. 892-903.